

An Algorithm for \mathcal{H}_∞ Optimization of a Linear Time Invariant System Using Singular Value Decomposition¹

Bradley T. Burchett²

Department of Civil and Mechanical Engineering
United States Military Academy
West Point, New York 10996

Mark F. Costello³

Department of Mechanical Engineering
Oregon State University
Corvallis, Oregon 97331

Abstract

Many classes of feedback control designs can be reformulated as a static output feedback optimization problem. Previous work by Burchett and Costello [1] has exploited direct ways to compute the \mathcal{H}_2 optimal output feedback gains using dyadic decomposition and analytic derivatives of the eigensystem. This work presents a modification of this technique with application to \mathcal{H}_∞ performance optimization. Analytic derivatives of the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) are central to this method. The method is applied to two aircraft flight control problems.

1. Introduction

An LTI system in state space form,

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\mathbf{x}} &= \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{L}\mathbf{w} \\ \mathbf{y} &= \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x} \\ \mathbf{u} &= \mathbf{K}\mathbf{y}\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

can be visualized in block diagram form as shown in Figure 1. While the feedback gain matrix is constant, the form is certainly applicable to dynamic compensators. Costello and Schulz [2] developed an algorithm to express open structure dynamic compensators with arbitrary variable parameters in the static output feedback form. This work will provide a means to optimize the variable parameters of a general structure dynamic compensator to an \mathcal{H}_∞ bound. As is well known, the \mathcal{H}_∞ norm of the system above is,

$$\|\mathbf{E}(j\omega)\|_\infty = \sup_{\omega} \max_i \{\sigma_i[\mathbf{E}(j\omega)]\} \quad (2)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{E}(j\omega) &= \mathbf{M}(\omega)\mathbf{T}_{z,w}(j\omega) \\ \mathbf{T}_{z,w} &= \tilde{\mathbf{C}}(s\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A} - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{K}\mathbf{C})^{-1}\mathbf{L}\end{aligned}$$

is the transfer matrix from disturbance to plant output, σ_i is the i th singular value of the closed loop system, and $\mathbf{M}(\omega)$ is a frequency weighting function. The gain matrix \mathbf{K} is determined such that the \mathcal{H}_∞ norm defined above is minimized. The notion of \mathcal{H}_∞ optimal control was initiated in 1979 by Zames [3]. Developments in this field through 1993 are well summarized in a tutorial paper by Kwakernaak [4]. The \mathcal{H}_∞ norm is optimal when the system response to the worst frequency content disturbance signal is minimized. The most commonly used algorithm today is the gamma iteration algorithm by Doyle, Glover, Khargonekar, and Francis [5]. Their algorithm involves iterative solution of Riccati equations. This work investigates the possibility of computing the optimal \mathcal{H}_∞ feedback matrix using a direct numerical approach. Derivatives for the numerical optimization technique are computed analytically using a modified algorithm for computing derivatives of eigensystems. The paper begins by developing a method to calculate first and second derivatives of the singular values analytically which is a modification of existing well known algorithms for computing eigensystem derivatives. The basic method is then applied to the \mathcal{H}_∞ optimal control problem. To illustrate the algorithms inherent characteristics, the method is applied to an aircraft flight control problem from the literature, and an educational hardware MIMO plant.

2. Derivatives of the Singular Values

The algorithm described here centers around relating derivatives of the SVD to derivatives of the Eigen

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²Assistant Professor, ib6198@usma6.usma.edu

³Assistant Professor, costello@enr.orst.edu

Figure 1: Block Diagram of Feedback System

system. The SVD allows us to rewrite an $n \times m$ matrix \mathbf{A} as,

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^T \quad (3)$$

The derivatives of the squares of the non-zero singular values can then be found using equations 4 and 5,

$$\frac{\partial \sigma^2}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} = \mathbf{v}_k^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} \mathbf{v}_k \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}^H}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} \mathbf{A} + \mathbf{A}^H \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} \quad (5)$$

In equations 4 and 5, \mathbf{p}_n is an element of the feedback matrix \mathbf{K} , and \mathbf{v}_k is the k th column of \mathbf{V} . In order to obtain partial derivatives of σ from partial derivatives of σ^2 , we use the power rule.

$$\frac{\partial \sigma^2}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} = 2\sigma \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} = \frac{\frac{\partial \sigma^2}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n}}{2\sigma} \quad (7)$$

In order to find the second derivatives, we differentiate equation 4 to obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \sigma^2}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n \partial \mathbf{p}_m} &= \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}_k^T}{\partial \mathbf{p}_m} \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} \mathbf{v}_k \\ &+ \mathbf{v}_k^T \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n \partial \mathbf{p}_m} \mathbf{v}_k + \mathbf{v}_k^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}_k}{\partial \mathbf{p}_m} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 (\mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{A})}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n \partial \mathbf{p}_m} &= \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{A}^H}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n \partial \mathbf{p}_m} \mathbf{A} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}^H}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_m} \\ &+ \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}^H}{\partial \mathbf{p}_m} \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} + \mathbf{A}^H \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n \partial \mathbf{p}_m} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

which indicates that we will need the partial derivatives of \mathbf{V} as well. Assuming the non-zero singular values

Figure 2: Block Diagram of Toy System

are not repeated, we can use Rudisill's [6] approach for vector derivatives:

$$[\mathbf{L}] \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathbf{V}_k}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} \\ \frac{\partial \sigma^2}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} \end{Bmatrix} = [\mathbf{P}] \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{V}_k \\ \sigma^2 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

$$[\mathbf{L}] = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{V}_k^T & 0 \\ \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{A} - \sigma^2 \mathbf{I} & -\mathbf{V}_k \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

$$[\mathbf{P}] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{A}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

The orthogonality of \mathbf{v}_k implies that

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}_k^T}{\partial \mathbf{p}_m} = \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}_k}{\partial \mathbf{p}_m} \right)^T$$

The second partial derivatives of the singular values are,

$$\frac{\partial^2 (\sigma^2)}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n \partial \mathbf{p}_m} = 2 \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \mathbf{p}_m} \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} + 2\sigma \frac{\partial^2 \sigma}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n \partial \mathbf{p}_m} \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \sigma}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n \partial \mathbf{p}_m} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 (\sigma^2)}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n \partial \mathbf{p}_m} - 2 \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \mathbf{p}_m} \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} \right) / 2\sigma \quad (14)$$

3. Derivatives of the Transfer Function Matrix

Consider the linear time invariant system given by equation 1. The specific makeup of the transfer function matrix will depend upon the designer's preference as to performance vector. Here we will show the transfer function matrix and derivatives specific to our example. We are designing for \mathcal{H}_∞ disturbance rejection, thus we want to minimize the \mathcal{H}_∞ norm of the disturbance to performance vector transfer function. A block diagram representation of this transfer function is given in Figure 2. The transfer function $\mathbf{T}_{z,w}$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{T}_{z,w} &= \tilde{\mathbf{C}}(s\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A} - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{K}\mathbf{C})^{-1}\mathbf{L} \\ &= \tilde{\mathbf{C}}(j\omega\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A} - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{K}\mathbf{C})^{-1}\mathbf{L} \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3: Comparison of Convergence Properties of the three Algorithms

Where we choose the performance vector to be

$$z = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{y} \\ q\mathbf{u} \end{Bmatrix}$$

The control weight q is a design parameter which we set to 0.1 for our numerical example. So the $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$ matrix is

$$\tilde{\mathbf{C}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C} \\ q\mathbf{K}\mathbf{C} \end{bmatrix}$$

and

$$\mathbf{T}_{z,w}^H = \mathbf{L}^H(-j\omega\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}^H - \mathbf{C}^H\mathbf{K}^H\mathbf{B}^H)\tilde{\mathbf{C}}^H \quad (15)$$

so the transfer function first derivatives are given as,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{T}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} &= \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{C}}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} \mathbf{G}(j\omega) \mathbf{L} \\ &- \tilde{\mathbf{C}} \mathbf{G}(j\omega) \left(-\mathbf{B} \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} \mathbf{C} \right) \mathbf{G}(j\omega) \mathbf{L} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

$$\mathbf{G}(j\omega) = (j\omega\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A} - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{K}\mathbf{C})^{-1} \quad (17)$$

and,

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{T}^H}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} = \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{T}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} \right)^H \quad (18)$$

where,

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{C}}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ q \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} \mathbf{C} \end{bmatrix}$$

The second derivative of the transfer function is given as,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{T}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n \partial \mathbf{p}_m} = \left(-\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{C}}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} \right) \mathbf{G}(j\omega) \mathbf{H}_m \mathbf{G}(j\omega) \mathbf{L}$$

Figure 4: Comparison of H2 and H Infinity Designs

$$\begin{aligned} &- \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{C}}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_m} \right) \mathbf{G}(j\omega) \mathbf{H}_n \mathbf{G}(j\omega) \mathbf{L} \\ &+ \tilde{\mathbf{C}} \mathbf{G}(j\omega) \mathbf{H}_m \mathbf{G}(j\omega) \mathbf{H}_n \mathbf{G}(j\omega) \mathbf{L} \\ &+ \tilde{\mathbf{C}} \mathbf{G}(j\omega) \mathbf{H}_n \mathbf{G}(j\omega) \mathbf{H}_m \mathbf{G}(j\omega) \mathbf{L} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{H}_n &= \left(-\mathbf{B} \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n} \mathbf{C} \right) \\ \mathbf{H}_m &= \left(-\mathbf{B} \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_m} \mathbf{C} \right) \end{aligned}$$

and,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{T}^H}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n \partial \mathbf{p}_m} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{T}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_n \partial \mathbf{p}_m} \right)^H$$

4. The Algorithms

We used three algorithms to compare the convergence characteristics with and without analytic derivatives of the cost. Essentially the cost is given by equation 1 applied to the transfer function matrix. We expect the \sup_w to occur at one of the system's natural frequencies. Thus, we find the system eigenvalues, and take the SVD at each of these frequencies. We preprend the vector of natural frequencies with a single frequency low enough to approximate the DC response. In our numerical case, we choose 0.01 rad/sec for this frequency. We then take the infinity norm to be the maximum of maximum singular values over this small set of frequencies. First and second derivatives with respect to the elements of the feedback matrix are then found at the supremum frequency. The first algorithm is the simplex optimization by Nelder and Mead [7]

Figure 5: Time Response of TRMS with default gains

Figure 6: Time Response of TRMS with H-infinity constrained gains

applied to the cost only. The second algorithm is the Quasi-Newton method of Broydon, Fletcher, Goldfarb and Shanno [8,9,10,11] applied to the cost and analytic first derivatives. The third algorithm is a full newton method applied to the cost, and analytic first and second derivatives.

5. Numerical Example

The first example we choose is the AIRC aircraft model by Maciejowski [12]. It has the desirable characteristic of two lightly damped modes that are separated in frequency. This will allow us to determine whether two competing peaks in the frequency response will have an adverse effect on the convergence of our descent method. Note that we determined the disturbance matrix as a random matrix with norm equal to that of the control distribution matrix (**B**) and zero elements where the control distribution matrix has them as well. The system matrices follow:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1.1320 & 0 & -1.0 \\ 0 & -0.0538 & -0.1712 & 0 & 0.0705 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1.0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.0485 & 0 & -0.8556 & -1.013 \\ 0 & -0.2909 & 0 & 1.0532 & -0.6859 \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.12 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 4.4190 & 0 & -1.665 \\ 1.5750 & 0 & -0.0732 \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

$$\mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.1957 & 2.1612 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 2.8264 & 0 & 1.5953 \\ 3.8891 & 0 & 0.2781 \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

The feedback matrix is thus 3x3, making the cost function space nine dimensional, and the Hessian 9x9. It is thus impossible to visualize the cost function contours.

6. Hardware Example

In order to further exercise the algorithm on a system with disturbances and modeling uncertainties, we optimized the PID gains for the Feedback Twin Rotor MIMO System (TRMS) [13]. This system is a two-degree of freedom model of a helicopter with freedom of motion in the pitch and yaw axes. The control system consists of four PID filters, \mathbf{PID}_{vv} , \mathbf{PID}_{hh} , \mathbf{PID}_{vh} and \mathbf{PID}_{hv} with pitch and yaw error signals as their inputs. Two of the filters feed into the corresponding axis control input, and the other two are ‘cross-axis’—that is, using the error signal for pitch, \mathbf{PID}_{vh} uses the error signal from the horizontal axis to contribute to the vertical control signal, and vice-versa. This example provides an excellent illustration of realizing a system with an open control structure (PID) as an output feedback problem, where the twelve PID gains are in the static feedback matrix. The system model was derived from empirical open-loop step response data of each axis as an independent unit. Thus, the inherent cross-coupling of the two axes is not included in our design model. The resulting composite system is twelfth order. These gains are then optimized using the algorithm above resulting in an \mathcal{H}_∞ optimized PID controller.

7. Conclusions

Figure 3 shows the convergence sequence of the various algorithms for the low-order example. It appears that analytic derivatives of the singular values greatly aid the convergence of this method. The methods using analytic derivatives converge in 7 and 5 iterations respectively. The simplex method takes approximately 6473 iterations and displays an oscillatory nature in Figure 3. This oscillatory nature is apparently the competing interests of the two lightly damped modes, however the authors cannot sufficiently explain why that behavior is not present in the other algorithms. I.E. directional information for frequencies other than the supremum frequency for the present optimization step is not considered in determining the search direction or step size. We also noted that stability and realizability were not guaranteed by the descent method. That is, the algorithm must check for closed-loop stability and real feedback gains at each optimization step. If either condition is violated, the optimization is stopped. Finally, each algorithm yielded a slightly different infinity norm and feedback matrix with the simplex method yielding the absolute lowest infinity norm and corresponding feedback matrix:

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.5747 & -10.6553 & 6.4549 \\ -0.5404 & -73.6616 & -5.3724 \\ -1.9429 & -16.0219 & 58.6512 \end{bmatrix} \quad (24)$$

Figure 4 compares the frequency response of \mathcal{H}_2 and \mathcal{H}_∞ designs for the low-order example $\mathbf{T}_{z,w}$. Magnitudes are given in raw numbers rather than dB to emphasize the differences between designs. The most notable difference is in the low frequency response—disturbance rejection in this region is much improved in the \mathcal{H}_∞ design. Also, the \mathcal{H}_∞ design makes the two lightly damped peaks almost equal in magnitude. The \mathcal{H}_2 has a single obvious lightly damped peak which is below both peaks of the \mathcal{H}_∞ design.

The TRMS time response with default gains supplied by Feedback Inc. is shown in figure 5. We show the system response with feedback gains calculated with an \mathcal{H}_∞ constraint in figure 6. In both cases, the vertical axis is responding to a square wave while the horizontal axis is simultaneously responding to a sine wave. The vertical response generally has a faster damped natural frequency. Due to the system cross-coupling, each step response of the vertical axis acts as a large disturbance to the horizontal axis. It is obvious from a cursory comparison of the plots that our gains result in a much quicker settling in the vertical axis, and good tracking in the horizontal axis just before the next step in the vertical.

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